

EFFECT OF MEAN LOAD LEVELS ON FATIGUE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF RANDOM SHORT FIBER INJECTION MOLDED COMPOSITES

V. M. Karbhari, A. Dolgopolsky
(Department of Civil Engineering, University of Delaware,
Newark, DE 19716, U.S.A.)

ABSTRACT

Fatigue crack growth and fracture toughness of random short fiber reinforced injection molded composites under different mean load levels is investigated. Experiments were conducted on single edge notched (SEN) specimens of PA 6.6 reinforced with glass fibers, subjected to tensile-tensile fatigue. Fatigue fracture toughness was studied in terms of energy release rates and a power law relationship. Fractographic studies of fatigue fracture surfaces were also conducted and change in mechanisms of fatigue crack growth under differing mean loads are identified. It is seen that the concept of fracture toughness as a material parameter is not appropriate, as the lower mean loads result in an increased fracture toughness.

INTRODUCTION

With the increased use of short-fiber reinforced (sfr) polymeric composites in engineering applications, their reliability under fatigue loading has become of growing interest. Defining the fatigue damage of composite materials is not simple, as the failure modes are quite different from those in isotropic materials. Short-fiber reinforced injection molded thermoplastics such as the one used in this study exhibit an even more complex microstructure. The heterogenous microstructure inherent in such materials leads to a distribution of submicroscopic and microscopic flaws, causing such stress concentrators as fiber ends, fiber-matrix interfaces, filler material and process induced defects to play important roles during the fatigue life of the material¹. Fatigue behavior is seen to depend on a variety of factors including fiber lengths and orientation, fiber-matrix interface quality and composition of the polymer matrix^{2,3}. Crack initiation is aided by the multitude of fiber ends and debonded interfaces present⁴.

One of the first to study fatigue crack growth in sfr composites were Thornton⁵, and Owen and Bishop⁶, who used fracture mechanics concepts to characterize fatigue crack propagation (fcp), and made attempts to access damage tolerance. Lang et al.⁷ studied the effect of short glass fibers on fcp in Polyamides noting that fcp resistance of nylon was significantly increased by the incorporation of short glass fibers. Voss and Friedrich⁸ reported a decrease in fracture toughness as a result of fiber addition to neat polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), wherein the composite toughness was described as a function of the matrix toughness and the composite microstructure. Wang et al.^{1,9,10} investigated the kinetics of fcp in a random sfr Sheet Molding Compound (SMC) using both a power law relationship between the crack growth rate and the cyclic stress intensity factor range, and a probabilistic treatment of the density and cumulative distributions of microcrack lengths and orientations. Fatigue degradation and changes in material stiffness due to microcracking were studied and an empirical fatigue damage growth law was presented. Dibenedetto and Salee² incorporated the effects of the maximum stress intensity factor (K_{max}), amplitude of the stress intensity factor (ΔK), threshold stress intensity factor (K_{th}), and the critical stress intensity factor (K_C) to analyse

data for fcp in graphite fiber reinforced Nylon 66.

The objectives of this study are to examine the effect of different mean load levels on the fracture toughness and fatigue crack growth of an injection molded composite, in terms of energy release rates and a power law relationship, as well as through fractographic studies of the fracture surface.

MATERIALS

Fig. 1 Micrograph of polished cross-section, showing preferential orientation of fibers.

The material used in this study was a short glass fiber reinforced nylon (Trade name : Zytel 70G33L R) supplied in injection molded tensile bar form by E.I. duPont de Nemours and Company, Inc. The particular material had 33 wt% (18% volume) glass reinforcement. Unlike characteristic injection molded composites the skin layers were not clearly distinguishable, although the preferential fiber orientation in the mold fill direction existed through the sample as seen in Figure 1. This particular material system was chosen because its mechanical properties had been characterized¹¹ and fatigue studies had been attempted earlier for stress corrosion cracking⁸ and to explain the fcp resistance by the addition of short glass fibers to Nylon⁷.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Notched specimens with a geometry as in Figure 2 were tested in tensile-tensile fatigue on an Instron Model 1321 servohydraulic load frame. A constant load regime was used with a sinusoidal cyclic waveform with a constant load ratio of 0.2. Load deflection curves obtained at increasing crack lengths were utilized to calculate incremental energy release rates, used in the determination of a fracture toughness parameter. Scanning electron microscopy was used to analyze the fracture surfaces, so as to determine the differences in fatigue fracture mechanisms under two different mean load levels. The loads chosen were $\sigma_{m1} = 27.7$ MPa and $\sigma_{m2} = 33.6$ MPa, representing 15% and 18% of the ultimate composite stress respectively. All tests were conducted at a constant frequency of 5 Hz. Further representative experimental details may be found in reference 12. The stress intensity factor range for the SEN geometry was obtained from

$$\Delta K = \Delta\sigma \sqrt{\pi a} Y (a/w) \quad (1)$$

where a is the total crack length; w , the width of the specimen, and $\Delta\sigma$, the stress range ($= \sigma_{\max} - \sigma_{\min}$). $Y(a/w)$ is a correction factor for finite specimen size.

$$Y(a/w) = 1.122 - 0.231(a/w) + 10.550(a/w)^2 - 21.710(a/w)^3 + 30.382(a/w)^4 \quad (2)$$

FATIGUE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

The objective of this paper is to show that fracture toughness of a sfr composite, such as the one used in this study is dependent on loading history, amongst other factors. This is done on the basis of three studies:

- (1) using the Paris - Erdogan power law
- (2) using the concept of critical energy release rate
- (3) using the Crack Layer Theory

1. Power Law Relationship

One of the simplest models used to correlate fatigue crack growth rate with the stress intensity factor range is the Paris - Erdogan power law

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C \Delta K^m \quad (3)$$

Despite the complexity in fatigue behavior of sfr composites, the power law has earlier been seen to adequately characterize f_{cp} ^{5,6,13}. Numerous variations of the power law^{2,8} have been suggested in the literature. However (3) was found adequate for the purpose of this study. The exponent m had earlier been thought of as a function of material variables, frequency and state of stress⁹, and was commonly taken as a material parameter indicative of the fracture toughness. Investigations have shown an explicit dependence on mean load levels and we propose to add it to the list of functions affecting the value of the exponent¹³. Computations for the sfr composite showed a difference in exponent values with a higher value of m for the higher mean load. Results of da/dN vs. ΔK are shown in Figure 3. It is apparent that the lower mean load level samples show an increased toughness, a conclusion that is borne out by the remaining studies.

2. Traditional Energy Release Rates

Traditionally fracture toughness has been explained on the basis of values of critical energy release rates (J_C). Figure 4 shows the substantial change in critical energy release rates between the two mean load levels. It is apparent that the specimens tested at the lower mean load levels show a significantly greater value of J_C , and hence represent a higher fracture toughness. Scanning electron microscopy confirms the difference on a qualitative basis. The higher mean load level samples show brittle matrix behaviour in which matrix fracture occurs without "ductile pulling". The samples tested at the lower mean load showed much more extensive "ductile pulling" and damage, indicating more energy dissipation through material transformation, apparent in the ductile behaviour in the stable crack propagation zone.

3. Crack Layer Theory

Fractographic and microscopic analysis has shown that a zone of transformed (damaged) material accompanies crack propagation¹⁴⁻¹⁷. This zone is similar in concept to the pulsating plastic zone developed by Rice¹⁸. Damage typically constitutes a layer adjacent to the fatigue crack and hence the system of the crack and the surrounding damage can be considered as a crack layer¹⁴. The Crack Layer Theory is a phenomenological theory based on the thermodynamics of irreversible processes²⁰, using internal variables, through the identification of forces and rates of active zone movement. A schematic of the crack layer is shown in Figure 5., wherein ρ is the damage density. The active zone is characterized by the rate of damage density $\dot{\rho}$ being positive. When the crack propagates through the active zone the stresses are released and damage growth ceases (inert zone). Thus crack layer propagation can be seen as a movement of the active zone in terms of translation and rotation of the zone as a rigid body, and active zone deformation in terms of expansion and deviatoric deformation. Considering only active zone translation, the law of rectilinear crack layer propagation can be derived using the principle of minimum entropy production as

$$\frac{dL}{dN} = \frac{\dot{D}}{\gamma^* R_1 - A_1} \quad (4)$$

where dL/dN is the average crack extension per cycle; \dot{D} , the rate of energy dissipated on damage formation and growth within the active zone; γ^* , the specific enthalpy of damage; R_1 is the translational resistance moment and A_1 is the energy release rate. Physically R_1 can be characterized by the total amount of transformed material within the active zone in resistance to crack propagation, or as an integral amount of damage formed per unit crack extension. \dot{D} can be expressed in the form

$$\dot{D} = \beta \ell_a J_1 \quad (5)$$

wherein β is a phenomenological constant with dimensions of sec^{-1} , and ℓ_a is the length of the active zone. The term γ^*R_1 in (4) is the energy required for active zone translation and can be determined through manipulation of (3), (4) and the conditions of global instability of the crack layer as

$$\gamma^*R_1 = \frac{\dot{D}}{(d\ell/dN)^{\dagger}} J_1 \quad (6)$$

Preliminary investigations using this approach have shown that specimens tested at the lower mean load levels have higher values for the energy required for active zone translation, corroborating earlier evidence of the fracture toughness being increased at lower mean load levels. This is linked to larger micro-ductile zones in the samples tested at the lower mean load level, where high energy expenditure for fcp is required. It is of interest to note that the values of γ^*R_1 obtained near catastrophic failure seem to approach a common value irrespective of the mean load levels, leading to the conclusion that γ^* could be treated as a material constant. A similar conclusion has been made from tests on commercial polycarbonate²¹.

CONCLUSIONS

- * Critical energy release rates associated with fcp vary significantly with the mean load level and hence cannot be considered as a material parameter.
- * The Paris - Erdogan power law relationship is applicable to fcp in the injection molded sfr composite used. The exponent m is seen to depend on the mean load level in addition to variables previously described.
- * Samples tested at the lower mean load levels are seen to have a higher fatigue fracture toughness value.
- * The Crack layer theory presents a methodology whereby the energy required for active zone translation is used to describe fcp. The differences in damage mechanisms and micro-material behavior under the two different mean load levels can easily be seen using this concept.
- * γ^* - the specific enthalpy of damage is hypothesized as a material constant.

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Fig. 2 Sample test specimen geometry.

Fig. 3 Cyclic crack growth rate plotted against stress intensity factor range ΔK .

Fig. 4 Crack growth rate vs. energy release rate \square higher mean load level, \blacksquare lower mean load level.

Fig. 5 Schematic of Crack Layer.